

ISOMERISATION OF BENZYLIDENE DERIVATIVES. PART I.

By H. S. JOIS, A. KUPPUSAMI AND B. L. MANJUNATH.

The red dibenzylidene compound obtained by condensing benzaldehyde with 4:6-dianilino-1:3-diaminobenzene, when boiled with alcohol, isomerises to a yellowish white substance, which is not hydrolysed by the action of dilute acids. Similarly the benzylidene compounds, prepared by condensing other aromatic aldehydes with the above diamine and with 4:6-*o*-toluidino-1:3-diaminobenzene, undergo isomerisation, whereas the dibenzylidene derivative of 4:6-mesidino-1:2-diaminobenzene remains unchanged. The results are interpreted on the basis of the formation of derivatives of dihydrofluorindene.

It had been observed by Manjunath and Jois (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1930, p. 163) that the red dibenzylidene compound, (I) obtained by condensing benzaldehyde with 4:6-dianilino-1:3-diaminobenzene (II) prepared according to Manjunath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 276), was easily converted on boiling with alcohol to an isomeric colourless compound. This was regarded as due to ring-closure having taken place with the formation of an isomeric heterocyclic compound, 1:3 dibenzylidihydrofluorindene (III).

Similar benzylidene compounds were prepared by condensing the amine (II) with salicylaldehyde, anisaldehyde, vanillin, piperonal and cinnamaldehyde.* Each of these could be isomerised to the corresponding dihydrofluorindene derivative. In every case the benzylidene compounds were bright red in colour, while the isomerised compounds were pale yellow

* Attempts to condense (II) with formaldehyde and acetaldehyde under varying conditions resulted in the formation of resinous bodies only.

and exhibited a bluish fluorescence in solution. The red compounds had much lower melting points than their isomers. The benzylidene compounds were easily hydrolysed by acids to give their parent substances but their isomers were quite unaffected on boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid for a long time.

The speed of isomerisation of the different benzylidene derivatives was found to vary considerably. The benzaldehyde derivative isomerises on boiling it with alcohol for an hour or two. The anisaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde derivatives take a slightly longer period. On the other hand, the vanillin and piperonal derivatives isomerise so readily that it is not possible to obtain the benzylidene compounds in a state of purity. This difference in the speed of isomerisation is probably due to the nature and orienting influence of the substituent groups present in the aromatic aldehyde used for condensation.

The benzylidene compounds prepared from 4:6-di-*o*-toluidino-1:3-diaminobenzene (IV) by condensing it with benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, vanillin and piperonal also underwent isomerisation. But the benzylidene compounds from 4:6-dimesidino-1:3-diaminobenzene (V) resisted all attempts at isomerisation. From this it follows that one of the two

equivalent positions 2' and 6' in the diamine (II) must be free for the benzylidene compounds to isomerise.

Experiments are in progress to determine the exact nature of the change that takes place during the isomerisations mentioned in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Dibenzylidene Derivative of (II).—The diamine (II, 1 g.) was dissolved in just the requisite amount of alcohol and while the solution was kept boiling, benzaldehyde (0.73 g.) in alcohol was added. The solution acquired deep red colour and was quickly filtered hot. On cooling beautiful red crystals were obtained which were immediately filtered off and rapidly recrystallised from alcohol as red plates, m.p. 168°. (Found: C, 82.2; H, 5.75; N, 12.0. $C_{32}H_{26}N_4$ requires C, 82.4; H, 5.6; N, 12.0 per cent.)

Isomerisation of the Benzylidene Compound (I).—The red compound was dissolved in alcohol and the solution refluxed for 2 hours. The

TABLE I.

Aldehyde used.	Properties of the benzylidene compound.	Properties of the isomer.	Mol. formula.	Period required for isomerisation.
Salicylaldehyde	Red prisms, m.p. 204°. (Found : C, 77.1; H, 5.4; N, 11.0%).	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 339°. (Found : C, 77.1; H, 5.3; N, 11.4%).	$C_{20}H_{20}O_2N_4$ requires C, 77.1; H, 5.2; N, 11.2%.	4.5 hrs.
Anisaldehyde	Red prisms, m.p. 176°. (Found : C, 77.7; H, 5.8; N, 10.8%).	Orange yellow crystals, m.p. 294.5°. (Found : C, 77.7; H, 5.6; N, 10.7%).	$C_{24}H_{20}O_2N_4$ " C, 77.6; H, 5.7; N, 10.6%.	3 hrs.
Vanillin	Could not be isolated	Yellowish brown needles, m.p. 313.5°. (Found : C, 73.5; H, 5.4; N, 9.9%).	" C, 73.4; H, 5.4; N, 10.0%.	Readily isomerises
Piperonal	Crude red material, m.p. 162.69° (isomerises during purification).	Bright yellow needles, m.p. 291°. (Found : C, 73.7; H, 4.9; N, 10.2%).	" $C_{24}H_{20}O_2N_4$ " C, 73.6; H, 4.7; N, 10.1%.	Readily isomerises
Cinnamaldehyde	Red prisms, m.p. 184.5°. (Found : C, 83.3; H, 5.8; N, 10.7%).	Yellow plates, m.p. 296°. (Found : C, 83.1; H, 6.0; N, 10.9%).	" $C_{28}H_{20}N_4$ " C, 83.2; H, 5.8; N, 10.8%.	3 hrs.

TABLE II.

Benzaldehyde	Red plates, m.p. 147°. (Found : C, 82.6; H, 6.2; N, 11.5%).	Pale yellow needles, m.p. 362°. (Found : C, 82.7; H, 6.2; N, 11.5%).	" $C_{24}H_{20}N_4$ " C, 82.6; H, 6.1; N, 11.4%.	3 or 4 hrs.
Salicylaldehyde	Red compound, m.p. 188°. (Found : C, 77.5; H, 5.9; N, 10.7%).	Bright yellow crystals, m.p. 305°. (Found : C, 77.6; H, 5.8; N, 10.8%).	" $C_{24}H_{20}O_2N_4$ " C, 77.6; H, 5.7; N, 10.6%.	10-12 hrs.
Vanillin	Could not be isolated	Yellow crystals, m.p. 306°. (Found : C, 73.9; H, 5.9; N, 9.7%).	" $C_{28}H_{24}O_4N_4$ " C, 73.7; H, 5.8; N, 9.6%.	Readily isomerises.
Piperonal	Red crystals, m.p. 179°. (Found : C, 72; H, 4.6; N, 9.7%).	Yellow needles, m.p. 285°. (Found : C, 74.4; H, 4.7; N, 9.7%).	" $C_{28}H_{20}O_4N_4$ " C, 71.2; H, 4.5; N, 9.6%.	$\frac{1}{2}$ hour.

solution slowly turned yellow and became fluorescent. It was then filtered hot and allowed to cool when pale yellow needles of the isomeric compound (III) separated, m.p. 282.5° . (Found: C, 82.3; H, 5.7; N, 12.1. $C_{32}H_{26}N_4$ requires C, 82.4; H, 5.6; N, 12.0 per cent).

The other benzylidene derivatives of (II) and their isomerisation products were prepared in a similar manner and their properties are given in Table I.

4 : 6-Di-*o*-toluidino-1 : 3-dinitrobenzene. — 4 : 6-Dichloro-1 : 3-dinitrobenzene (10 g.) was condensed with *o*-toluidine (18 g.) by heating the mixture to 150° for 15 minutes. The excess of the base and its hydrochloride were removed by extraction with dilute hydrochloric acid and then with warm water. The yellow material on crystallisation from alcohol melted at 198° . (Found: N, 14.9. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4N_4$ requires N, 14.8 per cent).

4 : 6-Di-*o*-toluidino-1 : 3-diaminobenzene. — The foregoing substance was reduced by refluxing it with boiling sodium hydrosulphide (Manjunath, *loc. cit.*), when the diamine (IV) was obtained as a greyish product. On recrystallisation from xylene it melted at 186° . (Found: C, 75.3; H, 7.1; N, 17.7. $C_{20}H_{22}N_4$ requires C, 75.5; H, 6.9; N, 17.6 per cent).

The amine (IV) was condensed with aromatic aldehydes, as described before, and the properties of the benzylidene derivatives and their isomerisation products are shown in Table II.

4 : 6-Dimesidino-1 : 3-dinitrobenzene and 4:6-Dimesidino-1:3-diaminobenzene. — Mesidine (Fittig and Storer, *Annalen*, 1868, 147, 1) was condensed with 4 : 6-dichloro-1:3-dinitrobenzene to give 4:6-dimesidino-1:3-dinitrobenzene. On recrystallisation from alcohol it was obtained as yellow needles, m. p. 201° . (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{24}H_{26}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.9 per cent).

It was next reduced with sodium hydrosulphide and the diamine (V), crystallised from alcohol, was found to melt at 152° . (Found: C, 76.9; H, 8.2; N, 15.1. $C_{24}H_{30}N_4$ requires C, 77.0; H, 8.0; N, 15.0 per cent).

Dibenzylidene Derivative of (V). — The diamine (V, 9.5 g.) was condensed with benzaldehyde (3.31 g.) in alcohol when a red crystalline dibenzylidene compound was produced, m. p. 119° . (Found: C, 82.9; H, 7.0; N, 9.9. $C_{38}H_{38}N_4$ requires C, 82.9; H, 6.9; N, 10.2 per cent). It was quite stable and did not isomerise on boiling with alcohol even after 16 hours.

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